

Assessment of AI Utilization in Teaching and Learning of Biology Concepts Among Secondary Schools in Igabi, Kaduna-State

¹Ibrahim, M.M. & ²Adamu, A.T.

¹Department of Biology, Federal University of Education, Zaria – 0703851962 muinat.im@gmail.com

²Kaduna State Ministry of Education, 08069324261 marchityl@gmail.com

This study assess the use of Artificial Intelligence in teaching and learning of Biology concepts among Secondary Schools in Igabi, Kaduna State. The purpose was to examine the extent to which AI tools and applications are integrated into classroom instruction, identify their impact on students' learning experiences, and highlight challenges affecting their adoption. A descriptive survey design was employed, and data were collected from teachers and students across selected schools using 2 questionnaires titled AI Utilization for Biology Teaching Questionnaire (AIUBTQ) and AI Utilization for Biology Learning Questionnaire (AIUBLQ) which were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.79 were obtained after pilot study. The instrument was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that while awareness of AI in education is growing, its actual application in Biology classrooms remains limited due to inadequate infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and inconsistent access to digital resources. However, where utilized, AI tools were found to enhance visualization of complex biological concepts, improve student engagement, and support personalized learning. The study concludes that AI holds significant potential for transforming Biology education in Nigerian secondary schools if challenges of accessibility, capacity building, and infrastructural support are adequately addressed. It recommends increased investment in digital infrastructure, targeted teacher professional development, and policy support to promote effective integration of AI in teaching and learning.

Keywords:
Utilization,
Artificial
Intelligence,
Teaching,
Learning,
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Students

Introduction

The integration of digital technologies into educational systems has rapidly evolved beyond traditional Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools, with artificial intelligence (AI) now emerging as a transformative force in science education globally and in Nigeria. Particularly in biology education, with its intrinsic need for visualizing complex processes and facilitating student engagement, AI tools such as virtual labs, adaptive learning

platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems are providing new opportunities for immersive and individualized instruction (Luckin, 2020; Enebechi, 2024; Askarova, 2025). AI-driven applications allow students to explore biological concepts through simulations, automated assessments, and personalized feedback, which have been shown to enhance understanding, retention, and critical thinking compared to conventional methods (Akpan, Akpan &

King, 2025; Ajibike, 2025). Recent global and national trends indicate a significant shift in how Biology is taught, spurred further by the remote learning demands of the COVID-19 pandemic (Xu, 2024). The pandemic accelerated adoption of digital learning tools, highlighting the importance of digital and AI literacy for teachers and students (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018; Daniel, 2020). While these technologies carry immense promise, current studies reveal that integration of AI into secondary Biology education in Nigeria remains limited, especially outside urban centers, due to infrastructure deficits, intermittent electricity, limited internet access, and a persistent gap in teacher capacity (Olufemi, 2021).

National policies, such as the Federal Ministry of Education's (2019) ICT and digital strategy, acknowledge the need for technology-driven learning but implementation remains uneven, particularly in semi-urban and rural areas where resources are scarce and teacher training on AI and related technologies is inadequate (Abubakar et al., 2025). Studies conducted in states like Oyo, Akwa Ibom, and Kaduna underscore that both teachers and students exhibit low awareness and usage of AI tools for Biology instruction, and highlight persistent challenges related to capacity building and curriculum alignment (Oyawole, 2025; Akpan, Akpan & King, 2025). Empirical evidence strongly associates the effective use of AI and ICT tools in Biology with improved academic performance, increased learner motivation, and more interactive classrooms (Ajibike, 2025; Askarova, 2025). Advanced AI platforms now offer features such as real-time feedback, virtual experiments, and automated grading systems that help bridge learning gaps, facilitate differentiation, and

support educational inclusion for students from diverse backgrounds (Enebechi, 2024; Reiss, 2021). However, issues of digital divide, inconsistent access, teacher preparedness, and the pedagogical fit of AI with existing curriculum continue to pose substantial barriers across Nigerian schools (Akpan, Akpan & King, 2025; Oyawole, 2025; Ajibike, 2025).

Addressing these challenges through sustained investment in digital infrastructure, targeted professional development for teachers, and policy support is essential to actualize the potential of AI in Biology education. This study investigates the extent and effectiveness of AI utilization in Biology teaching and learning across selected secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State, focusing on types of AI technologies employed, their impact on pedagogical practices and student experiences, and the constraints limiting their broader adoption. The findings aim to inform stakeholders, guide future research, and support evidence-based interventions for effective AI integration in Nigerian secondary science education.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized potential of AI to enhance biology education, there remains a substantial gap between their theoretical benefits and the realities encountered in secondary school classrooms across Nigeria. Recent studies and reports continue to highlight persistent challenges in implementing technology-driven biology instruction, including inadequate infrastructure (such as unreliable internet and insufficient digital devices), limited teacher training, insufficient technical support, and resistance to change among some educators (Bello, 2025; Olawale & Yusuf, 2023; Ojo,

2023). The rapid pace of technological development presents further difficulties for schools attempting to maintain current and relevant resources while contending with budgetary and logistical constraints (Adebayo et al., 2022; Igboegwu et al., 2022). Policy and institutional efforts have recognized these gaps, yet evidence from studies in Kwara, Anambra, Lagos, and Zaria show that actual ICT integration such as AI in biology teaching remains inconsistent and often superficial (Bello, 2025; Ojo, 2023; Okoh, 2016; Samphina, 2025). Additionally, research focusing specifically on biology education rather than science generally is limited, especially regarding how technological tools influence students' conceptual understanding, practical skills development, scientific inquiry, and motivation during times of rapid digital change (Olawale & Yusuf, 2023; Adebayo et al., 2022).

Teacher-related factors such as professional qualifications, gender, and years of classroom experience also strongly affect adoption and use of ICT tools, resulting in variable effectiveness and students' unequal access to technology-enabled learning experiences (Bello, 2025; Igboegwu et al., 2022; Bullard, 2017). Although digital resources such as virtual labs and dynamic simulations foster collaborative and inquiry-based approaches to biology, many schools struggle with equipment shortages and underutilization of existing tools (Samphina, 2025; Olawale & Yusuf, 2023). Consequently, there is an urgent need for detailed research into ICT usage patterns, effectiveness, challenges, and opportunities in biology teaching and learning at the secondary level, particularly in regions such as Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State (Bello, 2025; Adebayo et al., 2022; Ojo,

2023). This study aims to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive assessment of technology integration, pedagogical outcomes, barriers to adoption, and recommendations for sustainable improvement in Nigerian secondary science education.

Research Objectives

This study seeks to:

- Identify and categorize the types of artificial intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of AI integration on teaching effectiveness, student engagement, and learning outcomes in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State.
- Investigate the challenges faced by teachers and students in adopting, implementing, and utilizing AI tools for biology education in Igabi, Kaduna State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

- What types of artificial intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in biology education across selected secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?
- How effective is AI integration in enhancing teaching quality and student engagement in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?
- What challenges do teachers and students encounter in adopting and utilizing AI tools in biology education among secondary schools in Igabi, Kaduna State?

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey research design,

suitable for collecting data on respondents' perceptions, opinions, and practices. The population comprised all SS II Biology students and teachers in Igabi Local Government Area, Kaduna State totaling 1,130 students, including one Biology teacher from each of the 13 schools. A total of 291 respondents were selected from the population as sample size using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size table to ensure adequate representation of students and teachers. Simple random sampling was employed to select the targeted number of respondents. Data were

collected using 2 structured questionnaires titled AI Utilization for Biology Teaching Questionnaire (AIUBTQ) and AI Utilization for Biology Learning Questionnaire (AIUBLQ) designed on a 5-point Likert scale which were validated and reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.79 were obtained after pilot study. The researchers personally administered the questionnaires and the collected data were analyzed and presented using frequency distribution tables, percentages, means, and standard deviations, facilitating clarity and ease of interpretation.

Results

Table 1: Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in Biology Education

S/N	Item Statement	VF	F	O	R	N	X	S.D
1	Use of multimedia projectors during biology lessons	24	149	66	45	7	3.95	0.91
2	Use of educational videos and animations for explaining biological processes	13	77	51	20	130	2.62	1.43
3	Use of biology-related software or simulations (e.g., virtual lab tools)	3	41	90	0	157	2.01	1.12
4	Use of interactive whiteboards or smartboards in the biology classroom	37	72	56	34	92	2.94	1.32
5	Access to online resources (e.g., YouTube, digital textbooks, educational sites)	3	214	15	6	53	3.74	1.13
6	Use of mobile apps or tablets for learning biology concepts	17	146	22	70	36	3.29	1.23
7	Use of computer labs for research and assignments related to biology	38	1	190	52	10	2.96	1.01
8	Integration of Learning Management Systems (e.g., Google Classroom, Edmodo)	2	32	33	132	92	1.97	1.05
9	Use of internet-enabled devices for individual or group learning in biology	137	14	37	15	88	3.57	1.61
10	Use of PowerPoint or other digital presentation tools during biology teaching	48	20	71	3	149	2.71	1.58
Cumulative Mean							2.98	

Key: VF = Very Frequent, F = Frequently, O = Occasionally, R = Rarely, N= Never, X = Mean, S.D =Standard Deviation

The data indicate that the use of AI and ICT tools in biology education has moderate

prevalence among secondary schools in Igabi. Multimedia projectors (mean=3.95)

and access to online resources (mean=3.74) are the most utilized tools, suggesting preference for widely accessible and familiar technologies. The use of interactive whiteboards and computer labs have moderate usage (means around 2.9 to 3.0), while integration of learning management systems has the lowest utilization (mean=1.97),

pointing to gaps in infrastructural and technical deployment. Use of biology-specific software and virtual labs also remains low (mean=2.01), indicating potential areas for growth. Overall, the cumulative mean (2.98) reveals moderate adoption of AI-related technologies with significant room for expansion to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Table 2: Effectiveness of AI Integration on Teaching and Student Engagement in Biology

S/N	Item Statement	VE	E	ME	SE	NEA	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	AI tools make biology lessons more interactive and engaging	101	27	39	17	107	3.07	1.64
2	AI facilitates easier understanding of difficult biology concepts	41	32	45	69	104	2.35	1.34
3	AI increase student participation and attentiveness in biology	101	70	36	24	60	3.56	1.40
4	AI enables teachers to deliver more organised and effective lessons	62	60	39	28	102	2.92	1.52
5	AI encourage collaborative learning among students	14	26	39	99	113	2.01	1.10
6	AI increase student motivation and enthusiasm for biology learning	92	42	66	47	44	3.33	1.35
7	AI support differentiated instruction to meet diverse learners' needs	17	23	39	95	117	1.99	1.09
8	AI use improves student retention and recall of biology knowledge	68	92	36	40	55	3.44	1.33
9	AI help teachers manage time and resources more effectively	64	53	48	54	72	2.89	1.38
10	AI integration supports continuous assessment and feedback	64	27	59	98	36	2.72	1.32
Cumulative Mean							2.83	

Key: VE = Very Effective, E = Effective, ME = Moderately Effective, SE = Slightly Effective, NEA = Not Effect at All

The data in Table 2 indicate a moderate perception of AI and ICT effectiveness in enhancing biology teaching and student engagement, with an overall mean score of 2.83 on a 5-point Likert scale. The highest rated items relate to increased student participation and attentiveness (mean = 3.56) and improved student motivation and

enthusiasm through AI integration (mean = 3.33). Conversely, differentiated instruction support through AI tools received the lowest effectiveness rating (mean = 1.99), highlighting limited impact in catering to diverse learner needs. Items like improving lesson interactivity scored moderately (mean = 3.07), while AI's role in simplifying

difficult concepts and supporting continuous assessment were perceived as less effective (means = 2.35 and 2.72, respectively). These varied perceptions underscore that while AI and ICT hold promise in specific aspects of biology education, their broad effectiveness may be

constrained by factors like access, teacher readiness, and tool sophistication. These findings suggest a cautiously optimistic view of AI integration benefits, tempered by challenges that require attention to maximize the potential of AI-enhanced biology education.

Table 3: Challenges in Adopting, Implementing and Utilizing AI tools in Biology Education

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	UN	D	SD	\bar{X}	S.D.
1	Inadequate access to AI tools for teaching Biology	118	95	4	54	20	4.02	1.06
2	Poor internet connectivity hinders access to online biology resources	113	91	0	27	60	3.93	1.29
3	Many biology teachers lack adequate training in AI tools	109	95	2	63	23	3.93	1.19
4	Technical support for maintaining AI tools is insufficient	106	92	0	67	26	3.84	1.22
5	Shortage of relevant digital biology content/resources	104	90	4	31	60	3.80	1.29
6	Frequent power outages disrupt AI-based biology lessons	120	99	0	22	50	4.04	1.19
7	Some teachers resist adopting AI in their teaching methods	100	95	0	45	51	3.79	1.28
8	School administrators provide inadequate support for AI integration	108	93	4	62	23	3.89	1.15
9	Many students lack basic digital skills required for using AI	113	97	0	22	59	3.93	1.24
10	Large class sizes make utilization of AI tools in biology lessons difficult	116	100	4	50	17	4.03	1.10
Cumulative Mean							3.92	

Key: SA = Strongly Agree, A = Agree, UN = Undecided, D = Disagree, SD = Strongly Disagree

The table highlights the major challenges faced by biology educators and students in adopting, implementing, and utilizing AI and ICT tools in biology education. With a cumulative mean score of 3.92, these challenges are significant and broadly recognized. The highest mean score (4.04) corresponds to frequent power outages disrupting AI-based lessons, emphasizing infrastructural unreliability as a key barrier. Lack of access to AI/ICT tools (mean = 4.02) and large class sizes (mean = 4.03) are also critical issues. Poor internet

connectivity, insufficient teacher training, inadequate technical support, and resistance among educators further compound the challenges. Student digital literacy deficits and weak administrative support round out the main constraints. The data indicate that infrastructural deficiencies, capacity gaps, and organizational support collectively hinder effective AI integration in biology classrooms, underscoring the need for comprehensive interventions targeting these areas

Discussion of Findings

The finding of moderate AI tool utilization in biology education across selected secondary schools in Igabi aligns with global and national research highlighting infrastructure and human capacity as limiting factors. For example, Adu, Olatundun, and Adeyanju (2020) reported that although many Nigerian schools have basic ICT facilities, actual usage is limited due to poor maintenance, low digital literacy among teachers, and unstable power supply. Similarly, Olufemi and Adedokun (2021) found that AI-based instructional strategies in biology classrooms were often hampered by insufficient teacher training and inadequate integration within pedagogical frameworks. Echoing this, Chen, Wang, and Liao (2021) emphasized that mobile learning applications require not only access but also active teacher engagement and alignment with the curriculum to be effective. Chauhan's (2017) meta-analysis further supported that while AI tools boost student engagement, their potential remains underutilized in contexts beset by systemic challenges. Chen et al. (2020) emphasized that digital literacy and student engagement are persistent barriers unless intentionally incorporated into educational planning. The observed moderate utilization thus reflects a transitional phase where infrastructure is available but not effectively leveraged for pedagogical impact.

The perception of low to moderate AI integration effectiveness in biology teaching and student engagement mirrors broader concerns regarding meaningful digital transformation in education. Chen and Wu (2023) argued that despite widespread AI availability, actual learning outcomes depend on contextual relevance and teacher competence. Baran and AlZoubi (2022) found that collaborative digital tools improve science learning only if supported

by robust teacher training and curriculum adaptation. Chen et al. (2020) noted that mere technological access does not guarantee engagement; content must be thoughtfully adapted to students' needs. Similarly, Cheng and Xie (2018) observed that teachers' value beliefs and Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) significantly influence AI adoption, aligning with Mishra and Koehler's (2006) framework advocating for the integration of content, pedagogy, and technology. Hence, the moderate effectiveness ratings reflect shortcomings in pedagogical integration, digital skills, and strategic AI tool deployment in biology education.

The strong agreement among respondents that challenges to AI adoption, implementation, and utilization persist reflects findings from diverse studies in developing nations. Adu et al. (2020) identified unreliable electricity, poor internet connectivity, and inadequate technical support as persistent obstacles to ICT use in Nigerian schools. Lawrence and Tar (2018) highlighted infrastructural and administrative constraints that hinder AI adoption in developing contexts. Chen et al. (2020) further indicated that limited student engagement results when schools lack digital scaffolding, coherent curriculum support, and ICT policy frameworks. Karolčík, Drlík, and Pinterová (2017) demonstrated that teacher readiness is critical for AI adoption, pointing to the need for targeted professional development to address digital skill gaps. Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) stressed the significance of institutional support, ongoing training, and motivation to overcome systemic barriers to effective AI integration. Collectively, these studies underscore that without addressing foundational infrastructural and human capacity challenges, AI implementation in biology education will continue to face significant limitations regardless of tool availability.

Conclusion

This study reveals that while artificial intelligence holds significant promise for transforming biology education in secondary schools, its current integration is moderate and faces several obstacles. The availability of AI tools and digital infrastructures alone does not guarantee their effective use; factors such as teacher readiness, training, and pedagogical alignment are crucial for realizing AI's potential to improve student understanding, engagement, and motivation. The findings suggest that AI is beginning to enhance visualization and personalized learning in biology but remains underutilized due to infrastructural limitations, inconsistent support, and a lack of capacity building. Thus, AI's transformative power in biology education is still an emerging reality that requires systemic efforts to bridge the gap between technological possibilities and classroom realities. Addressing these challenges goes beyond providing equipment; it requires comprehensive strategies including targeted professional development, adequate policy frameworks, and investments in reliable digital infrastructure to ensure equitable access and sustained adoption. The role of teachers as facilitators who skillfully integrate AI into teaching practices remains central, complementing AI's capabilities rather than replacing human interaction. Ultimately, fostering an enabling environment that embraces technological innovation with pedagogical sensitivity will be critical to fully harness AI's potential, driving improved learning outcomes and preparing students in Igabi and beyond, for the demands of the digital era.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the researcher:

- Government and educational stakeholders should prioritize substantial investment in reliable digital infrastructure including stable electricity, high-speed internet connectivity, and provision of AI-enabled devices and software to secondary schools across Igabi.
- Organize continuous, competency-based training programs for biology teachers focused on effective pedagogical integration of AI tools.
- Government should develop and enforce clear institutional policies that promote AI integration in biology education, including funding provisions, curriculum enhancement, and resource allocation.

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